

VI International Forum on Teacher Education

EDITORIAL: PERSPECTIVES AND PRIORITIES OF TEACHER
EDUCATION IN TIMES OF
CHANGE, CHOICE AND CHALLENGE

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This publication highlights current trends in the development of teacher education in different countries of the world. Presenting the international research of scientists, this special issue argues for strengthening partnership between Russian and foreign researchers, who prioritize joint discussion of promising forms of scientific and methodological support for innovative teacher education, new developments and achievements in the field of educational technologies.

A special issue contains collections of papers presented at the VI International Forum on Teacher Education (IFTE 2020) which over years became a major international platform in psychology and education. Annually, distinguished scholars, experts and practitioners from all over the world take part in the discussions and share experience and insights into teacher education creating an ‘academic bridge’ between Russian and overseas educators. The Forum was held at the Kazan Federal University, one of the oldest higher educational institutions in Russia, celebrating its 216th anniversary this year. The University main priorities have always focused on training highly-skilled professionals and aspiring to become a top-level research center. Teacher education at Kazan Federal University has deep historical roots. Originated in 1812, the KFU system of teacher education has evolved into one of the largest and acknowledged in modern Russia. In 2020, KFU was ranked the 94th in the Times Higher Education World University Rankings in the subject area “Education” which is the result of profound scientific research and international academic collaboration.

IFTE 2020 theme was “Prospects and priorities of teacher education in times of change, choice and challenges”. The Forum comprised three international sub-conferences: “E-learning in teacher education”, “Teacher education for social justice, equality and culturally relevant pedagogy”, “Global trends and perspectives on bilingual and language teacher education”. First time in its history the Forum was held virtually due to the COVID-19 pandemic. Keynote lectures, synchronous paper sessions, symposia, round tables, workshops, and SIG meetings were held on the Microsoft Teams corporate platform.

More than 860 participants from 196 Russian and 79 overseas universities and research centers participated in the Forum (including scientists and practitioners from Azerbaijan, Belarus, Kazakhstan, Kyrgyzstan, Uzbekistan, Moldova, Austria, Bulgaria, the UK, Ireland, Germany, Israel, India, China, Malaysia, Poland, Slovakia, Slovenia, the USA, Turkey, Finland, Italy, Montenegro, France, Greece, Norway, Spain, Canada, the South Korea). According to Microsoft Analytics, there were over 32,000 logins during the Forum. According to Yandex.Metrica

statistics, from May 27 to June 9, 2020, 6463 unique users from 88 countries (including Russia) visited the Forum's official website. 20% of the users were foreign visitors.

IFTE 2020 became one of the largest virtual research venues in the world during the COVID-19 pandemic. Researchers from 275 universities, scientific and educational organizations presented reports on the problems of content modernization and development in vocational and teacher education, professional competencies and personality traits of twenty-first century teachers, integration of vocational and university teacher education in training modern teachers, improvement of continuous teacher education system and many other topics.

The Forum was supported by the Russian Academy of Education (RAE), the Russian Education Researchers Association (RERA), the Association of Science Editors and publishers of Russia (ASEP), the Turkish Education Research Association (TERA), the Association for Teacher Education in Europe (ATEE), the International Association of Educators (INASED), and the Cyprus Education Research Association (CERA).

This special issue features three collections of papers presented at IFTE sub-conferences. The first collection reveals the organizational, substantive and procedural aspects of teacher education, highlights the features of the authentic educational contexts of teacher training systems from around the world. The authors disclose aspects of digital didactics, define general strategies for digitalization of modern teacher education, substantiate innovative digital learning models. Also, contributors propose a system of comprehensive psychological and pedagogical support for all educational stakeholders in the new era. The second collection highlights different ways to overcome the problem of inequality in modern education. The researchers focused on disclosing and testing of mechanisms, methods and technologies for teaching children with special educational needs, solving the issues of inclusion in modern schools. The raised issues also included a methodology for organizing multicultural training of teachers who can effectively interact with migrant children and their families, defining institutional and pedagogical mechanisms that provoke and support inequalities in education. The third collection touches upon the issues of bilingual and language education in teacher training, focusing on new strategies, theoretical and practical aspects, and effective conditions of school-university partnership with regards to multicultural teacher training. Some articles illuminate language education as implemented through digital technologies, analyze various systems of formative assessment bilingual and language teacher training program outcomes. Further, authors substantiate the need for the professional development of a teacher-linguist in the context of standardization of education, underlining their cultural and professional identities.

IFTE 2020 Organizing Committee expresses their sincere gratitude to the members of the Forum scientific committee, represented by leading Russian and foreign scientists in the field of education, the editorial board which took the responsibility to ensure quality and authenticity control of papers. The Committee also acknowledges international scientific associations that provided information support to IFTE 2020 and Microsoft for technical support of the Forum.

The main theme of VII International Forum on Teacher Education (IFTE 2021) is "Teacher Education: New Challenges and Goals". The Forum will discuss the current problems of modern teacher education within three sub-conferences: "Teachers for Children with Special Educational Needs", "Education Trajectories in the Time of Extremes", and "Training Teachers as Moral Agents in the 21st century". The Forum will be held in a mixed format (offline and online) on 26 - 28 May, 2021 with the support of Microsoft. We look forward to fruitful cooperation further encouraged at IFTE 2021 that will contribute to the mutual enrichment of education systems around the world.